

ON THE MEAN VALUE OF THE SMARANDACHE DOUBLE FACTORIAL FUNCTION

Zhu Minhui

1 Institute of Mathematics and Physics, XAUEST, Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R.China

2 Department of Mathematics, Northwest University Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R.China

Abstract For any positive integer n , the Smarandache double factorial function $Sdf(n)$ is defined as the least positive integer m such that $m!!$ is divisible by n . In this paper, we study the mean value properties of $Sdf(n)$, and give an interesting mean value formula for it.

Keywords: F.Smarandache problem; Smarandache function; Mean Value.

§1. Introduction and results

For any positive integer n , the Smarandache double factorial function $Sdf(n)$ is defined as the least positive integer m such that $m!!$ is divisible by n , where

$$m!! = \begin{cases} 2 \cdot 4 \cdots m, & \text{if } 2|m; \\ 1 \cdot 3 \cdots m, & \text{if } 2 \nmid m. \end{cases}$$

About the arithmetical properties of $Sdf(n)$, many people had studied it before (see reference [2]). The main purpose of this paper is to study the mean value properties of $Sdf(n)$, and obtain an interesting mean value formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any real number $x \geq 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} Sdf(n) = \frac{7\pi^2}{24} \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem. First we need the following two simple Lemmas.

Lemma 1. if $2 \nmid n$ and $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ is the factorization of n , where p_1, p_2, \cdots, p_k are distinct odd primes and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \cdots, \alpha_k$ are positive integers, then

$$Sdf(n) = \max(Sdf(p_1^{\alpha_1}), Sdf(p_2^{\alpha_2}), \cdots, Sdf(p_k^{\alpha_k}))$$

Proof. Let $m_i = Sdf(p_i^{\alpha_i})$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Then we get $2 \nmid m_i$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) and

$$p_i^{\alpha_i} | (m_i)!!, i = 1, 2, \dots, k.$$

Let $m = \max(m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k)$. Then we have

$$(m_i)!! | m!!, i = 1, 2, \dots, k.$$

Thus we get

$$p_i^{\alpha_i} | m!!, i = 1, 2, \dots, k.$$

Notice that p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k are distinct odd primes. We have

$$\gcd(p_i^{\alpha_i}, p_j^{\alpha_j}) = 1, 1 \leq i < j \leq k.$$

Therefore, we obtain $n | m!!$. It implies that

$$Sdf(n) \leq m.$$

On the other hand, by the definition of m , if $Sdf(n) < m$, then there exists a prime power $p_j^{\alpha_j}$ ($1 \leq j \leq k$) such that

$$p_j^{\alpha_j} | Sdf(n)!!.$$

We get $n | Sdf(n)!!$, a contradiction. Therefore, we obtain $Sdf(n) = m$.

This proves Lemma 1.

Lemma 2. For positive integer n ($2 \nmid n$), let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ is the prime powers factorization of n and $P(n) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} \{p_i\}$. if there exists $P(n)$ satisfied with $P(n) > \sqrt{n}$, then we have the identity

$$Sdf(n) = P(n).$$

Proof. First we let $Sdf(n) = m$, then m is the smallest positive integer such that $n | m!!$. Now we will prove that $m = P(n)$. We assume $P(n) = p_0$. From the definition of $P(n)$ and lemma 1, we know that $Sdf(n) = \max(p_0, (2\alpha_i - 1)p_i)$. Therefore we get

$$(I) \quad \text{If } \alpha_i = 1, \text{ then } Sdf(n) = p_0 \geq n^{\frac{1}{2}} \geq (2\alpha_i - 1)p_i;$$

$$(II) \quad \text{If } \alpha_i \geq 2, \text{ then } Sdf(n) = p_0 > 2 \ln n n^{\frac{1}{4}} > (2\alpha_i - 1)p_i.$$

Combining (I)-(II), we can easily obtain

$$Sdf(n) = P(n)$$

This proves Lemma 2.

Now we use the above Lemmas to complete the proof of Theorem. First we separate the summation in the Theorem into two parts.

$$\sum_{n \leq x} Sdf(n) = \sum_{u \leq \frac{x-1}{2}} Sdf(2u+1) + \sum_{u \leq \frac{x}{2}} Sdf(2u), \quad (1)$$

For the first part. we let the sets \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} as following:

$$\mathcal{A} = \{2u + 1 | 2u + 1 \leq x, P(2u + 1) \leq \sqrt{2u + 1}\}$$

and

$$\mathcal{B} = \{2u + 1 | 2u + 1 \leq x, P(2u + 1) > \sqrt{2u + 1}\}.$$

Using the Euler summation formula, we get

$$\sum_{2u+1 \in \mathcal{A}} Sdf(2u + 1) \ll \sum_{2u+1 \leq x} \sqrt{2u + 1} \ln(2u + 1) \ll x^{\frac{3}{2}} \ln x. \quad (2)$$

Similarly, from the Abel's identity we also get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{2u+1 \in \mathcal{B}} Sdf(2u + 1) \\ = & \sum_{\substack{2u+1 \leq x \\ P(2u+1) > \sqrt{2u+1}}} P(2u + 1) \\ = & \sum_{1 \leq 2l+1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{2l+1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{2l+1}} p + O \left(\sum_{2l+1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{\sqrt{2l+1} \leq p \leq \frac{x}{2l+1}} \sqrt{x} \right) \\ = & \sum_{1 \leq 2l+1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x}{2l+1} \pi \left(\frac{x}{2l+1} \right) - (2l+1) \pi(2l+1) - \int_{\sqrt{x}}^{\frac{x}{2l+1}} \pi(s) ds \right) \\ & + O \left(x^{\frac{3}{2}} \ln x \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\pi(x)$ denotes all the numbers of prime which is not exceeding x .

For $\pi(x)$, we have

$$\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\ln x} + O \left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x} \right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{1 \leq 2l+1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x}{2l+1} \pi \left(\frac{x}{2l+1} \right) - (2l+1) \pi(2l+1) - \int_{\sqrt{x}}^{\frac{x}{2l+1}} \pi(s) ds \right) \\ = & \sum_{1 \leq 2l+1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{x^2}{(2l+1)^2 \ln \frac{x}{(2l+1)}} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(2l+1)^2}{\ln(2l+1)} \right. \\ & + O \left(\frac{x^2}{(2l+1)^2 \ln^2 \frac{x}{(2l+1)}} \right) + O \left(\frac{(2l+1)^2}{\ln^2(2l+1)} \right) \\ & \left. + O \left(\frac{x^2}{(2l+1)^2 \ln^2 \frac{x}{(2l+1)}} - \frac{(2l+1)^2}{\ln^2(2l+1)} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{1 \leq 2l+1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{x^2}{(2l+1)^2 \ln \frac{x}{2l+1}} &= \sum_{0 \leq l \leq \frac{\sqrt{x}-1}{2}} \frac{x^2}{(2l+1)^2 \ln \frac{x}{2l+1}} \\
 &= \sum_{0 \leq l \leq \frac{\ln x - 1}{2}} \frac{x^2}{(2l+1)^2 \ln x} + O\left(\sum_{\frac{\ln x - 1}{2} \leq l \leq \frac{\sqrt{x}-1}{2}} \frac{x^2 \ln(2l+1)}{(2l+1)^2 \ln^2 x}\right) \\
 &= \frac{\pi^2}{8} \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right). \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

Combining (2), (3), (4) and (5) we obtain

$$\sum_{u \leq \frac{x-1}{2}} Sdf(2u+1) = \frac{\pi^2}{8} \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right). \tag{6}$$

For the second part, we notice that $2u = 2^\alpha n_1$ where α, n_1 are positive integers with $2 \nmid n_1$, let $S(2u) = \min\{m \mid 2u \mid m!\}$, from the definition of $Sdf(2u)$, we have

$$\sum_{2u \leq x} Sdf(2u) = \sum_{\substack{2^\alpha n_1 \leq x \\ 2^\alpha > n_1}} Sdf(2^\alpha n_1) \ll \sum_{\alpha \leq \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sqrt{x} \ll \sqrt{x} \ln x, \tag{7}$$

and

$$\sum_{2u \leq x} Sdf(2u) = 2 \sum_{2u \leq x} S(2u) + O(\sqrt{x} \ln x) = \frac{\pi^2}{6} \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right). \tag{8}$$

Combining (7) and (8) we obtain

$$\sum_{u \leq \frac{x}{2}} Sdf(2u) = \frac{\pi^2}{6} \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right). \tag{9}$$

From (1), (6) and (9) we obtain the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} Sdf(n) = \frac{7\pi^2}{24} \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem.

References

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